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D5.1 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

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Abstract

This deliverable outlines CANDLE's communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy. It provides an initial stakeholder mapping and outlines communication, dissemination and exploitation goals, strategies and channels. It also outlines the related tracking mechanisms and KPIs.

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Statement of originality

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable, Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation plan, describes the planned communication and outreach strategy for the CANDLE project. It defines an action plan to be enacted by WP5 and followed by the whole consortium, striving to:

- **Raise awareness:** Engage with stakeholders and raise awareness of the project's work . Highlight the different NCDNs and promote the progress being made in our sibling projects, UNCAN.eu and EU-CIP.
- **Engagement of key stakeholders:** Continuously engage with the project's stakeholder groups defined in T5.2 and create a structure for them to be informed about and contribute to key project work. Ensure information is adapted accordingly for relevant stakeholders.
- **Publications and participation in conferences and events:** Promote the project's outputs and publish these results in papers and publications. Present CANDLE's outcomes to a broader audience at conferences and events, ensuring they are understood.
- **Facilitate post-project adoption of CANDLE:** Plan the next steps beyond the project's lifespan by addressing sustainability issues and making the project's outputs available through the CANDLE Resource Kit.

One of CANDLE's primary goals is to enable diverse stakeholders to make optimal use of cancer data. To achieve this, we need to start with an overview of who contributes what to the cancer data ecosystem by mapping the project's key stakeholders. Identification and stratification of key stakeholder groups is detailed in Chapter 2.

CANDLE employs various channels to engage with target stakeholders, including:

- Official CANDLE website
- Targeted communication campaigns through social media channels
- CANDLE newsletter
- Workshops and webinars
- Promotion of scientific publications to a broader audience

The successful implementation of the CANDLE communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy is managed by the Communication Team, in collaboration with the PMO (Project Management Office) and a working group consisting of consortium partners representing almost all project beneficiaries. Through the monthly WP5 meetings, the Communication Team provides updates and highlights on communication and dissemination, planned activities, and receives feedback and new ideas from the working group. A variety of tools and communication lines are used to support the project's communication and dissemination activities.

Specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are outlined in this document and will be monitored throughout the project.

1 Introduction

This chapter provides an outline of the deliverable's scope and objectives, its intended audience, and the document's structure.

1.1 Scope and objectives of the deliverable

This document presents an initial stakeholder mapping and the communication, dissemination, and exploitation plan for the CANDLE project. The communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy will be led by EMPIRICA (WP5 co-lead), executed within T5.1 and T5.2, and implemented by the entire CANDLE consortium. The goal of CANDLE's communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy is to maximise the project's impact and visibility of its outcomes throughout the project lifetime and beyond.

This deliverable aims to:

- Detail the communication strategy of the project, its goals, communication channels, and outlook
- Outline CANDLE's dissemination plan, objectives, and opportunities
- Introduce the CANDLE design guidelines and brand identity
- Inform the consortium and synergy projects about the CANDLE target stakeholder groups
- Indicate CANDLE's key exploitable results and intended exploitation per stakeholder group

1.2 Intended Audience

This deliverable is targeted at the CANDLE consortium and EU synergy projects.

1.3 Structure of the document

The deliverable is structured into six chapters:

- **Chapter 1** introduces the document and its objectives.
- **Chapter 2** provides an initial stakeholder mapping, with stratification according to EHDS Digital Business Capabilities and relation to National Cancer Data Nodes.
- **Chapter 3** outlines the project's communication plan, its goals, and chosen communication channels.
- **Chapter 4** presents the dissemination strategy, with its goals and opportunities.
- **Chapter 5** outlines the exploitation strategy, with key exploitable assets and a mapping to stakeholders.
- **Chapter 6** provides conclusions and planned next steps.

Communication and dissemination are elaborated in separate chapters to describe the distinct strategies and goals of these activities.

2 Stakeholder Mapping

As a Coordination and Support Action, CANDLE creates connections between diverse stakeholders and initiatives in the EU cancer ecosystem (research, policy, care) and the emerging European Health Data Space. One of its main goals is also to enable diverse stakeholders to make optimal use of cancer data. To achieve this, we need to start with an overview of who contributes what to the cancer data ecosystem.

Thus, this chapter maps and classifies these stakeholders to a) obtain an overview of our communication, dissemination, and exploitation target groups; b) provide input to the WP2 definition of National Cancer Data Nodes and their users; c) underpin the WP4 capacity building concept; d) better connect to synergy projects, especially UNCAN-Connect and EU-CIP. It also enables CANDLE to leverage its partners' networks better to reach out to stakeholders on different levels: individual (e.g., researchers, patients, healthcare professionals), organisational (e.g., healthcare providers, cancer data registries, EHR systems developers, industry...), ecosystem (policy makers, diverse associations), and EU projects and networks.

2.1 Relevant stakeholder groups

Table 1 provides an initial mapping of the primary and secondary stakeholder groups we target in CANDLE. It outlines their relevance for CANDLE and what we wish to achieve by reaching out to them. “Communication” lists group-specific goals that go beyond informing stakeholders about upcoming NCDNs, which apply to all groups. “Dissemination” lists what we want to share with these groups, for them to reuse and contribute to. “Exploitation” lists what we want to enable stakeholders to do with CANDLE outputs. While Chapters 3-5 outline the strategies for each outreach aspect separately. This table provides a high-level overview.

Table 1: Mapping of Relevant Stakeholder Groups

Stakeholder Group	Relevance	Outreach target
Research Organisations: Cancer Research Centres (including hospitals and clinical research centers), individual researchers universities and research institutes	Primary users of NCDN-enabled data and services which will analyse combined national/EU datasets and generate new evidence to feed the UNCAN-Connect platform. Candidates to become an NCDN (leading research institute/university)	Communication: Inform them about CANDLE’s role in enabling FAIR, interoperable cancer data via NCDNs and EHDS Dissemination: Show technical outputs and findings on data reuse; Involve them in co-creation (e.g., NCDN roadmap) Exploitation: Enable them to adopt the CANDLE maturation model and to integrate NCDN concepts into their data strategies
National Cancer Registries	A population-based data backbone present in most MSs, crucial for NCDN implementation, Potential candidates to become NCDNs -> primary beneficiaries of CANDLE guidance	Communication: Inform NCDNs about options for linking to National Cancer Registries (complementary, integrated, etc.). Dissemination: showcase recommendations and governance models linking registries with NCDNs and EHDS structures

Stakeholder Group	Relevance	Outreach target
		Exploitation: Enable registries to integrate their workflows into NCDN frameworks, using the CANDLE Resource Kit
Policy Makers: at EU, Member State, and regional level	Set priorities, regulations, and funding conditions for NCDNs; EHDS implementers. Member State Level: require assistance to set up the National Cancer Data Nodes and anchor them in existing MS infrastructures and national EHDS roles EU Level: EHDS and NCDN implementation; requires input from the MS level to provide a Cancer Data Node policy that considers Member State Diversity.	Communication: Inform about NCDNs' relevance for EHDS and EU cancer initiative implementation Dissemination: Show and involve them in NCDN (user) definitions and policy dialogue – primarily to address country-specific needs. Promote NCDNs as long-term structures, worthy of political support. Disseminate and discuss sustainability models for National Cancer Data Nodes and how they can link to existing structures. Exploitation: Enable them to use the maturation model to shape NCDNs in their context and define the interplay with existing institutions (EU, national, regional), and to apply policy recommendations
Patients: cancer patients, survivors, cancer patient organisations	Ultimate beneficiaries; wish better outcomes for patients and survivors; need to be involved in NCDN co-design and data sharing workflows; organisations represent patient voice in NCDN for co-design and policy dialogue	Communication: inform about NCDNs' role in patient-centric data sharing Dissemination: show how NCDNs can enhance patient care; involve patients in creating patient consent management and data altruism in at least two NCDNs Exploitation: CANDLE helps translate UNCAN-Connect research to EU-CIP
Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs)	National governance bodies for secondary use of health data; Potential candidates to become NCDNs -> primary beneficiaries of CANDLE guidance	Communication: inform about NCDNs' alignment with EHDS secondary use governance Dissemination: share possible models for the relation between HDABs and NCDNs (merging, collaboration, etc); invite to policy dialogue Exploitation: enable them to align national cancer data access processes to the CANDLE framework in a tailored way for their Member State
Healthcare providers and professionals	Key data producers and users at the point of care; implement clinical workflows and feed clinical data to NCDNs; Need to have simple ways to share cancer data for secondary use; Channels for implementing guidelines and innovation into clinical research practice	Communication: inform about NCDNs' benefits for clinical research and care Dissemination: Show how NCDNs link to clinical workflows; provide practical guidance for data sharing
EU Synergy projects: cancer projects, EHDS projects	Link to implementers of different aspects of the EU Cancer Initiatives and the EHDS: infrastructure, data models, MS-level actors, knowledge transfer,	Communication: Inform on joint objectives and complementary roles Dissemination: Show what CANDLE contributes to the EHDS and cancer project

Stakeholder Group	Relevance	Outreach target
	legal requirements, engagement of specific stakeholders, cancer sub-domains	ecosystems; disseminate cross-project interaction Exploitation: Hold joint campaigns and events to demonstrate the link of NCDNs with those building cancer data and the EHDS ecosystem; integrate shared tools in the CANDLE Resource Kit
Research Infrastructures (RI)	Already provide many proven good practices for health data sharing – organisational, technical, methodological. Anchored in the consortium, they can help CANDLE leverage existing standards and FAIR data principles. Organised along the national node principle, and therefore able to contribute services at the NCDN level Potential candidates to become (jointly) an NCDN (national nodes)	Communication: Inform NCDNs’ link to existing RIs and their role in the CANDLE consortium Dissemination: Engage them in sharing their data governance best practices, to inspire NCDNs Exploitation: Enable them to relate their governance structures to NCDN structures
Digital Health Agencies	Responsible Member State institutions for the primary use of health data	Communication: Show how NCDNs contribute to the cancer data ecosystem Dissemination: Disseminate NCDN practices for cross-border cancer data sharing
Industry: pharma, biotech, medtech	Technology providers and downstream users of harmonised data, targets for exploitation and innovation	Communication: Inform about upcoming NCDNs Dissemination: Disseminate technical and governance outcomes relevant for R&D Exploitation: Enable them to use better quality cancer data from NCDNs for innovation
Funders: Policy makers, insurers, cancer charities, and foundations	Fund cancer research and support for patients	Communication: Communicate the societal value of NCDNs in accelerating research impact and patient benefit
Digital Infrastructures: data and platform providers	Provide infrastructure, tools and services required for interoperable data sharing and analysis.	Communication: inform about NCDNs’ link to EHDS, UNCAN.eu, EU-CIP Dissemination: showcase API specifications, guidelines, frameworks from WP3 Exploitation: enable them to set up adequate infrastructure for NCDNs and/or connect to it in infrastructure deployments
Standard Development Organisations (e.g. HL7, IHE, LOINC, SNOMED)	Develop data standards for primary and secondary use of health data that NCDNs and the EHDS bodies need to consider	Communication: Inform about recommendations on how to use standards for cancer data that CANDLE will develop Dissemination: Share CANDLE recommendations on how to use standards

Stakeholder Group	Relevance	Outreach target
		for cancer data; involve them in review of existing standards Exploitation: Enable them to use CANDLE's solution for NCDN compliance with international standards
Wider public	Interested in EU and national health policy and spending of public funds	Communication: Inform about the value of sharing cancer data

2.2 Stakeholder Stratification

This chapter further stratifies these stakeholders, exploring their positions in the EHDS Digital Business Capabilities Blueprint and their roles in National Cancer Data Nodes. It also emphasizes synergy projects.

It is thus an overview analysis of the cancer data ecosystem, focused on CANDLE's necessities.

2.2.1 Stratification according to the EHDS Digital Business Capabilities Blueprint

One of CANDLE's main aims is to ensure that NCDNs are positioned as vital components within the European Health Data Space. These EHDS functionalities and actors are defined in the EHDS Digital Business Capabilities Blueprint published by DG Sante¹. Using this blueprint as a guide enables CANDLE to develop National Cancer Data Nodes that fit well with the European Health Data Space and minimise redundant functions, infrastructures, and applications. We see CANDLE as a way to enhance interoperability of EHDS functions in Member States – for cancer data and beyond.

Table 2 outlines our stakeholder group stratification according to the EHDS Blueprint Functions.

Table 2: Stakeholder group stratification according to EHDS Digital Business Capabilities Blueprint Functions

Function	Stakeholder Group and Explanations	Outreach target in CANDLE
Data Holder ²	National Cancer Registries, Healthcare providers, Universities, Researchers, Research Infrastructure, Industry, Funders, Patient Organisations: Hold health data that can be shared for secondary use: population-based, clinical datasets, metadata, real-world evidence, clinical data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raise awareness of t NCDNs that support development of the UNCAN.eu platform and patient information portal of ECPDC - Show how NCDNs can support them to make their data available for societal benefit, comply with EHDS requirements, and enhance data FAIRness and quality

¹ The framework consists of a very detail-rich mapping of data, users, infrastructure and applications within the EHDS for secondary use of health data. It is available to the EU digital health community. We do not include it here since it would not be legible.

² See also the definition of "health data holder" according to EHDS Regulation, Article 2.

Data User³	<p>Research Organisations, Universities, Research Infrastructures, Policy Makers, Patient Organisations, Industry, Funders:</p> <p>Apply for data access to obtain a data permit for secondary use (research, innovation, policy, regulatory evidence, standards developments)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raise awareness of their roles as cancer data users - Show how NCDNs can support access to cancer data - Engage them in dialogues on the definition of data users and NCDN users - Engage them in policy dialogues on NCDNs from the user perspective
Health Data Access Body	<p>Health Data Access Bodies</p> <p>Entities responsible for managing access to health data for secondary use on national level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engage in policy dialogues, to show different ways HDAB functions can tie in with NCDN functions - Emphasise CANDLE's support for tailored NCDN solutions at the Member State level - Discuss how to best integrate NCDNs into national EHDS infrastructures
Intermediation Entity⁴	<p>Research Infrastructures</p> <p>Perform the duties of specific categories of health data holders.</p>	
Trusted Data Holder⁵	<p>Experienced data holders who participate in the data permit process with the HDAB</p> <p>Designated by Member States</p> <p>Candidates to become NCDNs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Help understand their role vis-à-vis HDABs and NCDNs - Inform them of how NCDNs can help them process and collaborate with HDABs on data requests related to cancer data
SPE Operator	<p>Digital Infrastructures</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explore how they might provide SPEs for HDABs - Show CANDLE's inventory of SPE software tools used in cancer research and the related requirements, possibly for NCDNs to use
Natural Person	<p>Patients, wider public</p> <p>Subjects of personal electronic health data, taxpayers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aligning with EU-CIP to inform about health data literacy and sharing rights - Inform how National Cancer Data Nodes improve their data rights regarding cancer data within the EHDS
Other Stakeholders	<p>Wider public, funders, Standard Development Organisations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inform how NCDNs help drive the EHDS, especially useful for the fight against cancer -

³ See also the definition of “health data user” according to EHDS Regulation, Article 2.

⁴ See also EHDS Regulation, Article 50

⁵ See also EHDS, Article 72

* Digital Business Capabilities Roles not covered in this table: SPE Operator, Cross-Border Registries, Scientific and Ethical Board

This table shows that all functions except Health Data Access Bodies⁶ can be fulfilled by more than one stakeholder group. Also, one stakeholder group can fulfil more than one function within the EHDS blueprint. For CANDLE's outreach activities, that means we need to make clear the function and particular group being addressed.

Health Data Access Bodies have a special role, as they are: a) the only CANDLE stakeholder group that corresponds exclusively to one function; b) a candidate that can become an NCDN themselves; c) the most impactful type of institution on EHDS2 at Member State level; d) interacting intensely with data holders, data users, data intermediation entities and trusted data holders; e) incorporating in their institutions all five digital business capabilities outlined in the EHDS blueprint (Data Access Management, National Health Data Catalogues, Secure Processing Environments, Cross-Border Gateways, Operations and Deployment). Thus, CANDLE needs to build strong contacts with each Member State's HDAB and establish an interaction mode with the respective NCDN that aligns well with the national conditions.

We acknowledge that Health Data Access Bodies, Data Intermediaries and Trusted Data Holders are not established yet in most Member States at the time of writing – and will only be designated by 2027. To be able to involve them before, we will contact designated candidates for these roles, using our excellent contacts to Member States to identify these candidates.

2.2.2 Stratification according to relation to National Cancer Data Nodes

CANDLE aims to build NCDNs that meet their users' needs. Thus, this chapter stratifies the CANDLE stakeholder groups according to their interactions with the NCDNs

Table 3: Stakeholder Stratification According to their Interactions with NCDNs

Stakeholder group	Interaction with National Cancer Data Node
Research Organisations: Cancer Research Centres (including hospitals and clinical research centers), Universities, Research institutes, individual researchers	Direct: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Follow NCDN guidance to share and access cancer data, enhance data quality, and FAIRness - Co-create NCDN maturation model, contribute to national implementation roadmaps - Use CANDLE training material to embed NCDN practices into research workflows
National Cancer Registries	Direct: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential candidates to become NCDNs - Aligning with NCDNs and HDABs on cancer data sharing - Align processes and data models with NCDN governance - Publish metadata to national dataset catalogues in HDABs - Participate in the NCDN Network to harmonise population-based datasets

⁶ The role of Health Data Access Body can also be fulfilled by more than one entity in individual Member States. Yet, if this is the case, there will always be one designated primary HDAB.

Stakeholder group	Interaction with National Cancer Data Node
Policy Makers: at EU, Member State, and regional level	Direct: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Determine the outline of NCDNs, and links to existing EHDS and cancer institutions - Determine cancer strategies that the NCDNs are embedded in - Use NCDN work results for policy making - Engage in CANDLE policy Dialogue to align NCDN development with national and EU timelines
Patients: cancer patients, survivors, cancer patient organisations	Direct: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-define patient-facing NCDN features - Identify the NCDN services they would like to use Indirect: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Benefit from higher quality cancer care due to NCDN's work - Benefit from collaboration on content for EU-CIP
Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs)	Direct: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential candidates to become an NCDN - Coordinate with NCDNs on secondary use permits - Exchange on technical and organisational procedures, to enable clear data access and data use pathways - Engage in capacity building to standardise workflows - Exchange with NCDNs on particularities of cancer data
Healthcare Providers & Professionals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide NCDNs with clinical/EHR data quality indicators
EU Synergy Projects	Direct: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contribute standards, recommendations, and lessons learned to the CANDLE resource Kit - Help define EHDS guidelines and tools that also shape NCDNs - Align timelines of major cancer initiatives and EHDS milestones - Help shape the NCDN definition vis-à-vis other structures - Help disseminate the NCDN concept Indirect: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support NCDNs by creating a broader ecosystem
Research Infrastructures	Direct: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential candidates to become an NCDN (national nodes) - Interact with NCDNs as data users and holders via HDAB-approved pathways - Contribute their expertise on particular data types and national efforts
Digital Health Agencies	Indirect: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Handling cancer data for primary use, could potentially get inspired by NCDN cross-border practices
Industry	Direct: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide implementation feedback to improve NCDN collaboration with industry - Interact with NCDNs as data holders and data users via HDAB-approved pathways

Stakeholder group	Interaction with National Cancer Data Node
Digital Infrastructures: data and platform providers	Direct: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide infrastructure (like SPEs) for NCDNs - or linking to NCDN infrastructure - Link NCDNs to the EHDS infrastructure - Contribute reusable technical blueprints to the CANDLE Resource Kit - Contribute experience from SPEs in the cancer community
Standard Development Organisations	Direct: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop and curate standards for primary and secondary use of health data that NCDNs need to use - Can learn from NCDN's way to apply their standards to cancer data
Funders	Direct: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Align investments with NCDN maturity gaps identified in the maturation model - Use evidence from pilots to de-risk funding decisions - Coordinate with implementers on national set-up
Wider society	Indirect: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide societal feedback that influences NCDNs

Synergy Projects

Table 4: Suggested Synergy Projects

Project	Relevance to CANDLE
UNCAN-Connect	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Build UNCAN.eu as the main infrastructure linking NCDNs - Harmonise data/metadata models, identifiers, and consent flows for NCDNs to UNCAN.eu - Coordinate country roadmaps and pilots so NCDN onboarding supports UNCAN.eu use cases. - Align on SPEs, national Health Data Catalogues, and DAAMs
EU-CIP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Receive patient-centred data from National Cancer Data Nodes - Transform UNCAN.eu and NCDN insights into content for the ECPDC Needs input from NCDNs to encourage patients to engage with citizen research
EUCAIM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reuse interoperability & federation patterns for imaging (catalogues, SPE) - Coordinate dataset curation & access policies across NCDNs and EUCAIM - Share tooling/benchmarks for AI validation
Bigpicture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide tooling and guidelines for AI-development and validation at scale in digital pathology - Support HDAB in sharing pathology data; populate national catalogue with pathology datasets - Support cross-border use of pathology data for AI validation
TEHDAS2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Build guidelines for Health Data Access Bodies and thus the backbone of EHDS secondary structure in Member States

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NCDN structures need to align with TEHDAS2 guidelines to integrate into the national EHDS structure.
GDI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Align on GA4GH-based standards, access policies, and node roles - Connect national genomic nodes to NCDN catalogues/DAAMS/SPE - Share governance & security practices for cross-border use
ECHOS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Build national instances focused on cancer - Complement NCDN's data focus with a Cancer Mission Policy focus - Possibility to align on national roadmaps or help each other to engage different national actors
CancerWatch JA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National Cancer Data Registries are essential partners to reach out to actors in Member State cancer data ecosystems - Need to coordinate the interaction between registries and the National Cancer Data Nodes
EUnetCCC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide a link to the cancer treatment dimension and the primary use of health data - Possibility to coordinate training via CCC networks.
Jane2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possibility to involve the Network of Expertise to define NCDN roles and users
QUANTUM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Link to the dimension of data quality within the EHDS

This list could still be amended with numerous other cancer projects – e.g., 4P-CAN, CURTAIN, eCAN2, MAYA, Transcan IV. While we engage with these projects, we do not consider them a priority in the early stages of CANDLE.

3 Communication plan

This chapter of the deliverable elaborates on the project's communication strategy, outlining the communication goals, objectives, and key messages, and providing an overview of the communication channels and campaigns.

3.1 Communication goals and key messages

CANDLE is a project operating within Europe's Beating Cancer Plan and the EU Mission on Cancer: an ecosystem working to improve cancer prevention, early detection, diagnostics, therapeutics, and patients' quality of life. In this respect, the CANDLE project's main objective is to scale up and enhance existing national and international health data infrastructures. The project will ensure alignment of data infrastructure with EHDS regulations across Member States and resolve any barriers that jeopardize the effective implementation of the UNCAN.eu and ECDPC platforms. CANDLE will support the emerging NCDNs and engage stakeholders and initiatives to advance NCDN development.

Thus, the CANDLE communication activities aim to make these project goals understandable and approachable for the target audience, as outlined in Table 1. The communication objectives entail the following aspects:

- CANDLE project goals:
 - Promote development of NCDNs, their integration with UNCAN.eu and ECDPC, and alignment with EHDS regulations.
 - Make cancer data easily accessible.
 - Contribute to Europe's Beating Cancer Plan and the European Health Data Space (EHDS).
- CANDLE project progress:
 - Project deliverables
 - Project milestones
 - Meetings and events

3.2 Communication Channels

CANDLE uses multiple channels to communicate with relevant stakeholder groups. The following communication pillars and channels are elaborated upon in this section:

- Project branding
- Project website
- Newsletter
- Social media channels (LinkedIn and Mastodon)
- Communication campaigns
- Communication materials
- Events

3.2.1 Project branding

The visual strategy for the CANDLE communication and dissemination campaign is outlined in the project branding kit. This kit includes the primary and alternate project colour scheme, logos, typeface, and the EU funding logo. This kit ensures consistency among all communication campaigns and establishes a well-recognizable visual identity for the project.

Figure 1: CANDLE project logos

The primary CANDLE project logo was created before the project's start date and has been used in all CANDLE-related materials since. A few alternative versions of the logo are provided to ensure optimal visibility. The CANDLE design manual also includes a colour palette and fonts for use in visual and written materials.

Figure 2: CANDLE colour palette (left) and typeface (right)

In accordance with the CANDLE logo, colour scheme, and fonts outlined in the CANDLE design manual, PowerPoint and Word template documents were created for project presentations, deliverables, and other project documents.

Figure 3: CANDLE PowerPoint presentation template

Figure 4: CANDLE deliverable (left) and general document (right) templates

3.2.2 Website

Rationale

The project’s official website provides a gateway to all available knowledge about the project, including general information, its goals and ambitions, current activities, an overview of the consortium, past and upcoming events, and synergy projects. The website’s target audience includes all stakeholders the CANDLE project is planning to reach, as listed in Chapter 2. This website is the primary channel for all these stakeholders to stay informed about the project’s activities and updates by registering for the CANDLE newsletter.

Status quo

The website can be accessed at: <https://candle-project.eu/>. The website was built using the WordPress Content Management System and complies with the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) AA standards. The first version of the website was developed during July-August 2025. Following feedback on content and framework from the project partners and an initial test run, the website was launched on August 29th, 2025. The website launch was accompanied by a dedicated social media campaign, as well as an email notification to the consortium.

Figure 5: CANDLE website landing page and structure

The landing page has a user-friendly design, with identifiable headlines and direct links to the project’s social media channels—LinkedIn, Mastodon, and Zenodo—at the footer. The “Contact Us” option is available to all website visitors to contact the website management team with any project-related questions. The website is organized into the following main pages: an “About” page, a “Synergy Projects” page, “News” and “Events” sections, a “Resource Kit” page, and a “National Cancer Data Nodes” section. It also offers a newsletter subscription form for interested stakeholders to register and receive the CANDLE newsletter.

Outlook

The website will be continuously updated to reflect the latest progress made in the CANDLE project. The “Resource Kit” and “National Cancer Data Nodes” pages are currently empty, as the project is in its infancy and no outcomes have been generated. As relevant outcomes and updates become available, the pages will be populated. The expected outcomes include relevant project activities, accepted public deliverables, and other relevant achievements of project partners within the context of CANDLE. The “News” and “Events” sections will have the most updates, reflecting ongoing project work and providing readers with an opportunity to review past CANDLE updates.

In addition to the CANDLE project website, project partners may publish news items about their CANDLE work on their own websites to further disseminate the project. The consortium members’ websites are listed under the “About – Consortium” subpage of the project website.

3.2.3 Newsletter

Rationale

The CANDLE newsletter will provide an overview of the latest project updates to all interested stakeholders on a quarterly basis. The content of the newsletter will be based on the content of the website and social media channels, and will link back to more fleshed-out posts on these platforms. The highlight spot in the newsletter will be reserved for a project milestone, outcome, or significant event reported over the three months covered in each newsletter instalment.

The newsletter will be issued every three months, starting on M6. Each instalment will be disseminated on our social media channels and implemented on the project website.

Status quo

Interested parties can register to receive the CANDLE newsletter via the website's registration form. The newsletter registration tool requires an email address and the full name of the recipient.

Newsletter

Stay up to date on CANDLE's progress by signing up to our newsletter!

The screenshot shows a registration form with the following fields and elements:

- E-Mail***: A text input field.
- Salutation**: A dropdown menu with a hyphen (-) selected.
- First name***: A text input field.
- Last name***: A text input field.
- Yes, I want to subscribe to the CANDLE newsletter. I agree that my data will be used to process my request. For more information and disclaimer, see the [Privacy Statement](#).*
- Submit**: A green button.

Figure 6: CANDLE newsletter registration form

The website CleverReach is used to structure, send, and manage the CANDLE newsletter. CleverReach is a tool hosted in Germany and fully compliant with GDPR. The platform also provides broad customisation functions and analysis tools to personalise the newsletter and gauge its impact and readability. The newsletter framework upholds the aforementioned CANDLE branding kit.

The first edition of the CANDLE newsletter was published at the end of November and is also available on the project website.

Outlook

The CANDLE newsletter will continue to be published on a quarterly basis and will cover all upcoming project outcomes, communications, and other relevant topics.

3.2.4 Social media channels

Rationale

In addition to the project website, CANDLE employs the social media platforms LinkedIn and Mastodon to further the communication and dissemination efforts and highlight the project's activities and key outcomes. Both ad-hoc communications and planned social media campaigns are disseminated through these channels. This allows for continuous communication between the CANDLE project and a wider audience, and encourages interaction between the project and target stakeholder groups. Whenever possible, we aim to point the social media users back to the project website, where they can further engage with CANDLE.

Status quo

CANDLE's social media platforms were set up before the project's beginning date and were launched at project start. These platforms were chosen for their popularity among our target stakeholder groups and fellow EU projects. Project partner empirica is responsible for the social

media channels and communication, but all consortium partners are encouraged to engage with the official CANDLE accounts and share the campaigns with their respective networks.

Table 5: CANDLE Project social media channels

Platform	Account Name	URL	Followers (as of 4 November 2025)
LinkedIn	CANDLE Project	https://www.linkedin.com/company/candle-project/	424 followers
Mastodon	@CANDLEProject	https://eupolicy.social/@CANDLEproject	11 followers

The consortium is involved in communication and dissemination activities through the WP5 meetings, where they are informed about planned communication strategies, upcoming social media campaigns, and events. When we highlight specific partners or WPs on social media, we engage in bilateral communication with the relevant consortium partners to refine the campaign.

LinkedIn

The project page launched on 1 June 2025, accompanied by a press release announcing the start of the CANDLE project and its core work. The post garnered 2,116 impressions, with 68 likes and 12 reposts. Our consortium partners also shared the press release on their own social media channels.

Figure 7: The CANDLE project press release and first LinkedIn post

Since then, the CANDLE LinkedIn account has consistently shared updates on the project’s progress, its representation at events, coordinated social media campaigns, and updates from partners. Besides our original posts, we have also shared posts highlighting CANDLE and updates from our sister projects, UNCAN.eu and EU-CIP. The account has amassed 424 followers since June and continues to grow.

On LinkedIn, we aim to reach our target stakeholders with more content-rich, long-form posts that share the message in detail. This platform is ideal for communicating with professional networks and fellow EU projects, as the platform itself is professional-oriented. The information and posts we share on this platform closely mimic the website posts, but we aim to redirect the readers to the official CANDLE website whenever possible. The CANDLE project continuously receives positive feedback and engagement via the platform.

Figure 8: CANDLE LinkedIn posts

Mastodon

The CANDLE Mastodon page launched on 1 June 2025, also accompanied by a press release announcing the start of the CANDLE project. Mastodon is a very specialized social media network, centered around EU projects and related institutions; therefore, it provides us with the opportunity to communicate directly with “our peers”. On the other hand, the platform has a small community. The platform focuses on short-form content, and we aim to redirect readers to the official CANDLE website for a more detailed overview. The account has amassed 11 followers since June and continues to grow.

Figure 9: CANDLE Mastodon posts

Outlook

The social media channels will continue to be systematically updated with all relevant news from the CANDLE-verse throughout the project lifetime. Regular social media campaigns will be planned around project outcomes, milestones, and important events.

3.2.5 Communication campaigns

Rationale

The CANDLE website and social media channels are at the forefront of the project's communication campaigns. The communication efforts combine ad hoc communication and planned campaigns and series, aiming to keep target stakeholders engaged with the project and highlight our achievements at every stage.

Status quo

When creating a communication campaign, a defined key message and target group are essential for its success. The WP5 communications team structures the campaign, including ideas for social media posts (a core message for LinkedIn and a 500-character post for Mastodon), supporting visuals, and, when necessary, a blog post or news item for the project website. A communications package including these drafts and posting guidelines (campaign timeline, goal, and material use) is sent to the project management team. Specific social media campaigns might include video interviews, informative videos, or filmed footage of events. When the communication campaign refers to one particular partner's work on the project or a WP, this package is also forwarded to the relevant project participants for review of the content for scientific accuracy.

WP5 tracks the impact of each social media campaign using social media analytics tools. We have drafted possible communication campaign ideas covering a range of topics, all of which need to be agreed upon with the respective WP leaders. The topics and timing of these campaigns have been chosen according to project deliverables and milestones worth communicating to target stakeholder groups. Time buffers between milestone/deliverable completion and holidays have been accounted for.

Status quo

The table below provides an overview of current considerations for social media campaigns.

Table 6: Past and planned communication campaigns

Campaign No.	Topic	Content Lead	Month	Status
1	Project Start – Press Release	EMPIRICA/HEALTH-RI	1	COMPLETED
2	Website Launch	EMPIRICA/HEALTH-RI	3	COMPLETED
3	CANDLE WP Introduction	EMPIRICA/HEALTH-RI/LYGATURE/ELIXIR/BSC/FICAN	5	ONGOING
4	#BehindtheMission with UNCAN-Connect and EU-CIP	EMPIRICA/HEALTH-RI/NETHUB/BBMRI-ERIC	9	PLANNED
5	CANDLE 2026 General Assembly	EMPIRICA	12	PLANNED
6	UNCAN.eu Users	ELIXIR/CRG	12	PLANNED

7	CANDLE Personas	EMPIRICA/STEINBEIS/ECO	14	PLANNED
8	FAIR Cancer Data	EMPIRICA/HEALTH-RI	18	PLANNED
9	Best Practices for Cancer Data Use	ECRIN/BBMRI-ERIC	22	PLANNED
10	Challenges in cancer care	EMPIRICA/HEALTH-RI	24	PLANNED
11	CANDLE 2027 General Assembly	EMPIRICA	24	PLANNED
12	NCDN Network Progress	LYGATURE/EMPIRICA/HEALTH-RI	30	PLANNED
13	NCDN Success Stories	ELIXIR/CRG	34	PLANNED
14	CANDLE Resource Kit	LYGATURE/EMPIRICA/HEALTH-RI	36	PLANNED
15	CANDLE Final Meeting	EMPIRICA	36	PLANNED

Regular ad-hoc campaigns will be shared to disseminate project updates, external event participation, project assemblies, and updates from our sister projects UNCAN-Connect and EU-CIP. WP5 will draft the campaigns and maintain strong collaboration with the project management team to determine when event promotion and calls to action are needed. Events open for registration will be advertised in advance to encourage our target audience to register and participate. Events that are invite-only will not be disclosed on social media, but a post-event news item will be shared to communicate lessons learned.

3.2.6 Communication materials

We created additional communication materials to provide general information about the project and to funnel interest into newsletter sign-ups, stakeholder group participation, and other calls to action. A project flyer, project presentation, and roll-up banner complement the online communication channels.

Project Flyer

Figure 10: CANDLE Project Flyer

The CANDLE flyer sports a concise, two-sided DIN A5 format, following the project’s branding guidelines. The content is structured around three pillars: what CANDLE is, how it works (project

workstreams and links to UNCAN.eu/ECPDC/EHDS), and the impact it generates, complemented by project facts and contacts. A PDF of the flyer is available on Zenodo.⁷

The cover page opens with a one-sentence purpose statement, and also features a visual and the website address. The middle double-page spread features a “Concept” segment that outlines the project’s work approach. An infographic positions NCDNs in relation to the UNCAN.eu platform, the ECPDC information platform, and key stakeholders, linking it to the principal CANDLER workstreams.

A section on outcomes and impact outlines what CANDLER will deliver and the impact we aim to achieve. On the back cover, a panel summarises the project facts. Calls to action—“Empower Europe’s fight against cancer and join the CANDLER initiative!”, “Join the Stakeholder Engagement Group”, “Sign up to the CANDLER Newsletter”—and contact conclude the page, alongside the EU funding acknowledgement with the grant number 101214368.

The flyer conveys key information at a first glance, supporting early-stage awareness and stakeholder onboarding across events, meetings, and digital channels.

Project Presentation

Figure 11: CANDLER Project Presentation

The CANDLER project presentation is the standard slide deck for briefings, conferences, and stakeholder meetings. It introduces CANDLER’s purpose, defines National Cancer Data Nodes (NCDNs), presents facts and figures, and summarises objectives, methodology, and calls to action. The visual language follows the project’s design guidelines. It is available on Zenodo.⁸

This deck ensures that every partner communicates a consistent, DoA-aligned story about the NCDN concept, the EHDS connection, and the joint pathway with UNCAN.eu/ECPDC. It is structured to support early-phase awareness and stakeholder onboarding.

⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/17524408>

⁸ <https://zenodo.org/records/17524336>

We consider the slides a core project presentation to which speakers can add specific modules— e.g., WP updates and Member State-specific material.

Project Roll-Up Banner

The CANDLE roll-up banner features the full project name and three central bullet points summarising the project’s work. The lower part displays a visual and the EU funding statements.

The banner aims to draw attention to CANDLE’s presence at face-to-face events, like conferences, fairs, and meetings. It conveys the project’s key elements at one glance.

The text was intentionally kept short to avoid information overload.

Figure 12: CANDLE Project Banner

4 Dissemination strategy

This chapter outlines CANDLE’s dissemination strategy, highlighting its goals and the dissemination opportunities we aim to pursue.

4.1 Dissemination goals

Overall, the main goal of the CANDLE dissemination activities is to maximize the visibility, accessibility, and uptake of the project’s findings beyond the consortium itself. The following dissemination objectives were outlined to achieve this overarching dissemination goal.

Dissemination Objectives (DO)

- **DO1 - Raise awareness:** Engage with stakeholders and raise awareness of the project’s work in national and international cancer data infrastructures. Highlight the different NCDNs and promote the progress being made in our sister projects, UNCAN.eu and EU-CIP.
- **DO2 – Engagement of key stakeholders:** Continuously engage with the project’s stakeholder groups defined in T5.2 and create a structure for them to be informed about and contribute to key project work. Ensure information is adapted accordingly for relevant stakeholders.
- **DO3 – Publications and participation in conferences and events:** Promote the project’s outputs and publish these results in papers and scientific publications. Present CANDLE’s outcomes to a broader audience at conferences and events, ensuring they are understood.
- **DO4 – Facilitate post-project adoption of CANDLE:** Plan the next steps beyond the project’s lifespan by addressing sustainability issues and making the project’s outputs available through the CANDLE Resource Kit.

4.2 Dissemination opportunities

We will use diverse dissemination channels to make our results available to a domain-specific public that is likely to reuse them. Apart from communication on the channels outlined in chapter 3.3, we will use events and publications for an exchange that is richer in content.

4.2.1 Events

CANDLE will use events to share results in greater detail. These events include presentations by synergy projects, contributions to the European Commission’s project cluster meetings (“Understanding” and “Quality of Life”), and participation in international conferences.

Table 7: Targeted conferences and meetings for CANDLE presentations/participation

Conference Name	Comment
Cluster Meetings: Understanding Cancer and Quality of Life	Important alignment to fellow EU projects in both clusters. CANDLE will participate as oriented by the European Commission
EACR Annual Congress	Flagship European cancer research meeting; strong audience for NCDN/EHDS-aligned methods.
ESMO Congress	Leading European clinical oncology forum; connects with CCCs and policy/registry stakeholders.

HIMSS Europe	Europe's key digital-health conference; strong EHDS, interoperability, DAAMS/SPE audiences.
TEHDAS2 Stakeholder Fora	Strong audience of EHDS implementers for secondary use – particularly Health Data Access Bodies.
European Health Data Protection Congress	Privacy, AI, governance—core to EHDS-compliant NCDN dissemination.
EOSC Symposium	Important audience on FAIR data and European research infrastructures (domain-agnostic)
European Public Health Conference	Important audience for contextualising National Cancer Data Nodes as public health instrument.
European Cancer Summit	Meaningful connection to broader European Cancer Policies
EUNetCCC Annual Meeting	Link to comprehensive cancer centres and the broader EU Cancer ecosystem
European Digital Health Summit	Meaningful connection to digital health challenges in Member States and the EU4Health Programme.

Table 8: Event Participations June-November 2025

Event Name	Date	CANDLE Contribution
Dutch oncology node meeting	25.06.2025	Health-RI, Lygature, and IKNL participated in connecting CANDLE to national stakeholders.
ABRE Advances in Biomedical REsearch symposium ABRE2025, Tenerife	21-23.07.2025	Lifang Liu (Health-RI) spoke in a panel with ECHOS, UNCAN-Connect, and EU-CIP on the EU Cancer Data Ecosystem. (news item)
15th 1+MG Meeting, Copenhagen	10.09.2025	Lifang Liu (Health-RI) presented CANDLE and aligned on genomics dimension (news item)
EUnetCCC Annual Meeting 2025, Paris	6.-7.11.2025	Panel presentation by Tomi Mäkelä (FICAN) and CANDLE exhibition booth (news item)
Symposium - Making cancer data accessible for all, through cBioPortal, Amsterdam and online	11.11.2025	CANDLE (via Health-RI and NKI) organised this event to bring together cBioPortal developments from EOCS4Cancer with national efforts.
Building Bridges in Digital Health Innovation: Data, Policy & People, online	17.-18.11.2025	Carola Schulz (empirica) spoke about NCDN's role in privacy-preserving sharing of cancer data.

Figure 13 ABRE Symposium 2025 - Panel Discussion

Figure 14 CANDLE Project Booth at EUnetCCC Annual Meeting 2025

Figure 15 cBioPortal Symposium – Making Cancer Data Accessible for All - Opening by Gerrit Meijer

4.2.2 Publications

We aim to publish at least four papers as part of the CANDLE work. All publications will duly acknowledge EU funding for the CANDLE project and will be licensed under open access whenever possible. They will be uploaded to Zenodo and the Funding and Tenders Portal (as part of the periodic reporting).

Table 9: Targeted Journals for CANDLE publications

Publication	Importance of CANDLE
European Journal of Cancer	Outreach to European Oncology Audience
JAMA Oncology	High impact on the audience in oncology and translational science
Cancer Research	Outreach to AACR / ACS-related audience
Nature Cancer / British Journal of Cancer	Outreach to a broad oncology public
Bioinformatics	Link to important methods and standards relevant to CANDLE data integration
Genomics	Link to the genomics community

Information Services and Use	Outreach to the community around management, repositories, and FAIR data practices
Health Data Science	Outreach to the community on health data science, methods, and infrastructures
Journal of Big Data	Outreach to communities on big data infrastructures and governance

Zenodo

Available deliverables, presentations, and other text-based project outputs (e.g., communication materials) will be uploaded to the CANDLE Zenodo Community,⁹ under the CC-BY license. Upcoming project outputs will be uploaded to the platform as they are approved. This provides us with a FAIR distribution format of our outputs, making them available to the scientific community and producing accurate metadata.

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/candle-project/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

5 Exploitation strategy

Our exploitation strategy aims to enable our target groups to use CANDLE’s project results, take up our outcomes, and contribute to creating impact.

To this end, this chapter will first provide an initial list of the project’s key exploitable results and then match it to specific stakeholder groups.

5.1 Key exploitable results

Key exploitable results are project results that are especially promising for our target stakeholders and have a lasting impact on the ecosystem. CANDLE project objectives are anchored in the project’s concept, while the respective work packages put them into action.

All key exploitable results are compiled in the CANDLE Resource Kit, which serves as a “starter kit” for establishing and operating an NCDN. Yet, the respective components can also support cancer data actors individually. Table 10 outlines the key exploitable results, linking to project objectives and associated Work Packages.

Table 10: CANDLE Key Exploitable Results

Project Objective	Exploitable Result	Associated WPs
<p>O1 – Conceptualise National Cancer Data Nodes (NCDNs) at the technical, operational, policy, and Ethical, Legal, and Social Implications (ELSI) levels, addressing users’ needs by integrating best practices from European life science infrastructures and health data access and sharing. Ensure that NCDNs enable seamless interaction with the UNCAN.eu and ECPDC platforms to advance cancer research and patient care.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conceptualisation of the National Cancer Data Nodes and their users (D2.1): reusable, but flexible NCDN design reference for authorities and implementers. - Report on Data Users’ needs and solutions (D2.2): input for designing NCDN services - Best Practices in Cancer Data Utilisation for National Cancer Data Nodes (D2.3): guidelines for data handling within the new NCDNs, co-created with the cancer research community - NCDNs’ maturation levels in relation to the UNCAN.eu digital platform, including recommendations for continuous improvement (D3.1): implementation paths for NCDNs to technically align research data, software and the overall platform to the UNCAN.eu platform - Report outlining the NCDNs requisites for ECPDC, including patient data access control (D3.2): defining requirements for NCDNs to link to ECPDC and being a source for patient-centric data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WP2 - WP3
<p>O2 - Identify challenges and barriers at the national and EU levels, including technical, regulatory, operational, and ELSI-related barriers, that may hinder the implementation of UNCAN.eu and ECPDC platforms. Propose operational solutions to overcome these</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recommendations on maximising opportunity and overcoming potential barriers to effective implementation of UNCAN.eu and ECPDC (D2.4): exploring challenges that implementing NCDNs on a national and regional level might face regarding cross-border access to data. - Document outlining best practices/recommendations EHDS-compliant 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WP3 - WP2 - WP5

<p>barriers, ensuring that NCDNs support compliance with the European Health Data Space (EHDS) infrastructures for the primary and secondary use of data.</p>	<p>development of NCDNs (D3.3): recommendations on linking to primary and secondary use EHDS structures, focusing on data standards, quality, security, and transfer processes</p>	
<p>O3 – Develop exemplar national implementation roadmaps, tailored to the specific maturity level of an exemplar country, to guide policy dialogue and support the establishment of NCDNs. Roadmaps will account for differences in national readiness, tackle inequalities in data infrastructure, enhance knowledge transfer to small and widening countries, and address population subgroups with poor digital skills or limited digital resources.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CANDLE Maturation Model (MM) (D4.1 + D4.2): maturity framework for NCDNs to self-assess on governance, data quality, interoperability, and translational challenges. Including selected pilot countries - National Implementation roadmaps (T4.2): Individual pathways towards NCDN implementation that consider the national priorities and the health system - Core skills and knowledge exchange of NCDNs based on the CANDLE Maturation Model to tackle inequalities and build capacity (D4.3): Core skills and learning pathways for NCDN development – with special focus on small and widening countries - Roadmap toolkit (in D5.4 CANDLE Resource Kit): templates/checklists to co-create country roadmaps aligned with EHDS. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WP4 - WP5
<p>O4 – Establish and maintain a robust policy dialogue with a diverse set of stakeholders, including national and EU-level representatives from patients, the public sector, academia, digital health, industry, and professional societies. This dialogue will catalyse the development and implementation of NCDNs and ensure that all relevant voices contribute to policy formulation and the upscaling of cancer data infrastructures.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy dialogue report and recommendations (D5.3): Actionable policy guidance for the national level, derived from policy dialogue events and the Policy Dialogue Group (WP1) - Evidence from maturation model and roadmaps (T4.2): feeds into policy recommendations - Conclusions of the meetings of 'Understanding' and 'Quality of Life' clusters (D5.6): contextualisation of policy aspects of NCDN implementation with other EZ projects - CANDLE will also generate a set of best practices for facilitating data donation for research purposes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WP5 - WP1
<p>O5 – Foster the upscale and sustainability of NCDNs by consolidating guidance, tools, and best practices in the CANDLE Resource Kit. Establish a Network of NCDNs to facilitate knowledge exchange, collaboration, and continuous improvement. The CANDLE Resource Kit will provide templates, checklists, and best practices for aligning with EHDS, ensuring FAIR data principles, and promoting long-term sustainability of cancer data infrastructures.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CANDLE Resource Kit (D5.4): consolidated repository of best practices, checklists, Maturation Model toolkit, roadmap templates, National Cancer Data Node personas, and policy recommendations for national reuse, shared with open CC-BY license. - NCDN Network (T5.4): National Cancer Data Node (and possibly National Cancer Mission Hubs) exchange forum with onboarding services (orientation interviews; progress meetings) to carry adoption beyond the action. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WP5 - WP2-4

5.2 Matching exploitation to users

One of the ultimate goals of CANDLE and the National Cancer Data Nodes is to enhance the trinity of data on diagnosis, treatment, and outcomes.

This subchapter outlines how the targeted stakeholder groups can best use our key exploitable asset. We give special focus to National Cancer Data Nodes, as they are the primary beneficiaries of CANDLE's outcomes and can leverage the project's results for the greatest impact.

5.2.1 National Cancer Data Nodes

As anchored in the project objectives, National Cancer Data Nodes are, by definition, the primary target audience for all of CANDLE's outputs. As outlined in Chapter 2, future National Cancer Data Nodes can be anchored in different institutions that serve other targeted stakeholder groups (e.g., Ministries, Research Infrastructures, National Cancer Registries, Health Data Access Bodies). CANDLE's outputs help them become national references to enhance cancer data practices – in data capture, models, processes, etc.

The CANDLE Resource Kit is their toolbox for setting up National Cancer Data Nodes that meet requirements and consider national priorities. They can use the kit to:

- Define what services are expected of NCDNs: 1) Establish national cancer data nodes for cancer data holders; 2) Improve data quality of cancer data at source; 3) Ensure all cancer datasets have a metadata record in the EU dataset catalogue; 4) Develop common dataset variables for cancer datasets; 5) Provide tools for cancer data analysis to be used in secure processing environments (SPEs)
- Define how these services can be provided in the national context
- Understand what users they are serving
- Refine a plan towards NCDN operationalisation, based on national implementation roadmaps
- Assess their own maturity, with self-assessment tools from the maturation model
- Exchange with other NCDNs and possibly European Cancer Mission Hubs, to discuss operational challenges, best practices with UNCAN.eu and ECPDC platforms, connect to other national cancer and digital health infrastructures, and national RI nodes and EHDS

5.2.2 Research Organisations: Cancer Research Centres, individual researchers

Research organisations can benefit from the National Cancer Data Nodes by using more comprehensive and higher-quality cancer data. This enhances research capabilities across Europe. Most of these are indirect benefits that research organisations have from NCDN implementation. One concrete, directly usable example is CANDLE's approaches to standards and terminology that do not adequately address cancer data needs.

5.2.3 National Cancer Registries

CANDLE equips National Cancer Registries with the tools to initiate dialogue in countries where National Cancer Data Nodes do not yet exist. As mandatory national-level structures, National Cancer Registries are essential entry points and possibly ambassadors of the National Cancer Data Node concept. The CANDLE Resource Kit helps them fulfil this role by pointing to a resource decision-makers can use.

5.2.4 Policy Makers: EU, Member State, and regional level

CANDLE's key exploitable results help policymakers:

- Interact with UNCAN.eu on the national and regional level
- Assess their national cancer data ecosystem regarding priorities, maturity, and link to the EHDS
- Use the maturation model results to prioritize investments
- Obtain inspiration for health data ecosystems for other health topics
- Coordinate better with other cancer initiatives
- Link to the Member State perspective on cancer data

5.2.5 Patients: cancer patients, survivors, cancer patient organisations

Patients benefit indirectly from the improvements in research, care, data access, and patient information that National Cancer Data Nodes bring. CANDLE facilitates:

- Better prevention, early detection, diagnostics, and treatment
- Sustainable ways for patients to access their own data through EHDS infrastructures for primary use
- Better information to patients on the ECPDC platform

One more direct benefit would be the CANDLE personas, which would help better understand the National Cancer Data Nodes infrastructure and patients' roles in it.

5.2.6 Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs)

Health Data Access Bodies are important partners in embedding National Cancer Data Nodes within Member State structures for secondary use of health data. They can use above all WP3 on how NCDNs link to the national EHDS structures, notably:

- Linkage of Data Access Management Systems (DAAMs) and Secure Processing Environments (SPEs) to National Cancer Data Nodes
- Connection of National Health Data Catalogues to potential catalogues in National Cancer Data Nodes
- Inspiration on cross-border data sharing for cancer data
- Stakeholder feedback on the link between National Cancer Data Nodes and HDABs from WP5

5.2.7 Healthcare providers and professionals

Healthcare providers and professionals can, above all, leverage CANDLE's training modules to upskill in digital health literacy and related topics, such as cancer data quality.

5.2.8 EU Synergy projects: cancer projects, EHDS projects

UNCAN-Connect and EU-CIP will benefit from specific WP3 Deliverables that guide the technical and structural connections of the National Cancer Data Nodes to the platforms they are building.

UNCAN-Connect can directly exploit CANDLE's and the Resource Kit to accelerate the integration of Member States into UNCAN.eu and avoid duplication of efforts on the national level:

- The guidelines in D3.1–D3.3 offer various tools to connect to NCDNs, complying with the EHDS: e.g., templates for metadata catalogues, DAAMS, and SPEs
- CANDLE's policy-dialogue outputs (D5.3) and stakeholder maps will help UNCAN-Connect fine-tune national implementation efforts and identify key policy interlocutors

- The Maturation Model helps assess where more investment is needed to integrate Member States into the UNCAN.eu infrastructures

EU-CIP can mainly exploit CANDLE's assets that connect to ECPDC and are more patient-oriented:

- Personas and user-journey findings (D5.2)
- ECPDC alignment guidelines (D3.2)
- Communication materials embedded in the Resource Kit

ECHOS can use part of the guidelines in the Resources Kit to refine their European Cancer Mission Hub setup. If the Cancer Mission Hubs choose to participate in the National Cancer Data Nodes Network, they can also exchange experiences on connecting to existing national governance structures regarding cancer.

As an EHDS-focused project, TEHDAS2 can benefit from CANDLE's guidelines for linking National Cancer Data Nodes to the digital business capabilities of Health Data Access Bodies. Particularly relevant are CANDLE's EHDS. The Resource Kit and NCDN Network provide a demonstration environment for EHDS2 concepts in the context of cancer data.

5.2.9 Research Infrastructures (RI)

ESFRIs and RI nodes can use several CANDLE resources to refine their own cancer data sharing structures:

- WP2 cancer data sharing best practice and standards mapping
- the Maturation Model to benchmark national nodes
- Resource Kit (built on RDMKit/1+MG frameworks) to publish reusable intermediation patterns. RIs can align national node services, broker federation with UNCAN/ECPDC, and contribute domain learning paths and SOPs into the Kit for durable reuse

5.2.10 Digital Health Agencies

Digital Health Agencies benefit from CANDLE's work in facilitating cross-border cancer data exchange, as well as in the primary use of health data. It can use parts of WP3's work on EHDS integration at the legal, infrastructure, and governance levels.

5.2.11 Industry: pharma, biotech, medtech

Industry can use the CANDLE Results Kit to explore new ways to collaborate with NCDNs for cancer research. More indirectly, it will benefit from higher-quality cancer data available.

5.2.12 Digital Infrastructures

Digital infrastructures can exploit WP3 results on EHDS-compliant developments and the Resource Kit sections with guidance on health data catalogues, DAAMS and SPEs.

5.2.13 Standard Development Organisations

SDOs can use CANDLE's review of commonly used standards, vocabularies and codes and our recommendations for areas to areas where current standards are not specific to cancer. These will be part of the CANDLE Resource Kit. They can also benefit from the CANDLE maturation model that helps Member States self-assess where they stand in terms of interoperability and compliance with international standards.

5.2.14 Funders: Policy makers, insurers, cancer charities

Funders – especially policymakers – can use the maturation model to determine funding priorities for cancer data initiatives aligned with the EHDS. Cancer charities and insurers benefit more indirectly by having higher-quality data available to back up their investment decisions.

5.2.15 Wider public

The wider public benefits somewhat indirectly through better connections of cancer data at the Member State level, leading to better diagnosis, treatment, and outcomes.

5.3 Exploitation sustainability

The sustainability of CANDLE outputs is closely linked to that of the National Cancer Data Nodes. Especially, the Results Kit and the NCDN Network are tools to help Member States set up and implement National Cancer Data Nodes. The more Member States set up Nodes, the more likely these assets will be used.

For long-term sustainability, NCDNs need stable funding and to establish themselves as key infrastructure in national cancer data ecosystems and beyond. These two factors depend heavily on the individual national set-up of the Nodes: e.g., whether and in which existing institutions they will be integrated, and how they will interact with national EHDS infrastructures and the existing cancer data ecosystem. While CANDLE has no mandate to influence these aspects, its maturation model, implementation roadmaps, and Resource Kit will provide comprehensive guidance for Member States to develop plans that suit the national contexts. Also, by involving pilot countries that already have governmental support, we enhance the likelihood that National Cancer Data Nodes will be further implemented after the project ends.

Regarding project outcomes, sustainability beyond NCDNS, CANDLE's partnership with European (cancer) research infrastructures (e.g., EATRIS, EIRENE, ELIXIR, Euro-BioImaging) will facilitate the integration of CANDLE outputs into research ecosystems and clinical infrastructures, thereby increasing the likelihood that they are maintained post-project.

6 Communication, dissemination, and exploitation tracking

This chapter outlines the communication, dissemination, and exploitation tools and structures to be used by CANDLE, namely:

- The communication team and structure
- Communication and Dissemination Tracker
- Internal Project Communication

6.1 In-project communication structures

The CANDLE Communication Team is responsible for managing and coordinating the project's promotional materials, communication, and dissemination activities. WP5 lead Empirica leads communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities in the CANDLE Project under Task 5.1. Partners EKT and CRIHBM contribute to T5.1. The communication team leaders are responsible for preparing communication topics and content production for our social media channels and the official CANDLE website, as well as organising dissemination activities at external events such as conferences, webinars, and workshops.

The Communication Team's progress is tracked through monthly meetings, part of the WP5 monthly meeting. These meetings provide a dedicated platform to gather feedback from consortium partners on past and ongoing communication and dissemination efforts, coordinate promotion, explore new campaign ideas, and leverage available communication synergies.

The WP5 communication and dissemination team is responsible for staying up to date on social media and disseminating the latest news and updates. Since this is primarily ad hoc communication, it is conducted regularly without extensive review by other project members or coordination. For coordinated communication and dissemination campaigns focused on specific topics, project achievements, or events, the communication team follows a different process. All beneficiaries and WPs are responsible for informing WP5 of their participation in external events where they will be representing the CANDLE project, to ensure proper dissemination pre-event and a post-event report of their involvement. The WPs regularly inform WP5 of their latest efforts and achievements, as project communication also depends on what is regularly achieved and completed.

When reporting on upcoming events, internal and external, the communication leads devise an initial social media campaign. Such campaigns are typically comprised of one or multiple text posts associated with topic-specific graphics, as described in Section 3.2.5. The draft is reviewed by the coordination team and any relevant project members (e.g., event participants).

When planning a coordinated social media campaign spanning multiple weeks, the communication team develops a concept note to share with the project management team. The concept note includes an elaboration of the campaign's idea, its aim, and its perceived impact. This document also includes a posting schedule (if the campaign will be disseminated in multiple instalments), the text post(s), and the associated graphic(s). This concept note is forwarded to the management team and relevant project partners for review. When we highlight specific partners, WPs, or detailed scientific topics on social media, we engage in bilateral communication with the relevant consortium partners to create the content and refine the campaign.

Once the communication campaign has been reviewed and, if necessary, changes made, the material is disseminated through the appropriate CANDLE channels.

6.1.1 Link to internal project communication

Proactive communication between the communication team and project partners is key to ensuring a successful communication and dissemination strategy. The communication team maintains a strong line of communication with the PMO to collaborate efficiently on communication and dissemination efforts. Through the monthly WP5 meetings, the communication team keeps the project partners informed about developments in the communication and dissemination aspects of the project and encourages partner involvement. The CANDLE SharePoint, which includes a dedicated WP5 folder containing all communication and dissemination materials in an editable format, enables easy offline collaboration.

The flow of internal project communication has been established in the CANDLE Project Handbook (D1.2).

6.2 Key performance indicators

WP5 has identified measurable Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to track and report project communication and outreach activities. The chosen indicators and targets align with the communication goals and target stakeholders described in previous chapters, as well as the KPIs included in the project Grant Agreement. This table includes Key Performance Indicators for Mastodon, which are not reflected in the Grant Agreement. The indicators listed below will be consistently monitored through social media and website analytics, as well as the project tracking mechanism described in Chapter 6.3.

Table 11: CANDLE Communication and Outreach KPIs and Project Targets

ID	Indicator	Method of Measurement	3-Year Target
1	Number of Communication Campaigns	Project Reporting	12
2	Number of Followers on LinkedIn	LinkedIn Statistics	800
3	Number of Mastodon Followers	Mastodon Statistics	25
4	Number of Unique Website Page Views	Website Statistics	25 000
5	Number of Newsletters	Newsletters on Website	9
6	Number of Workshops (online & in-person)	Project Reporting	20
7	Number of Uploads on Zenodo	Zenodo Community	15
8	Number of Journal Articles Published	Submitted Papers	4
9	Number of Contributors to Conferences	Conference Reporting	10

6.3 Tracking mechanisms

A dedicated communication, dissemination, and exploitation tracking tool has been set up since the beginning of the project. This tool, in the form of an Excel spreadsheet, provides a smooth overview of communication and dissemination activities across the consortium. The tool is located in the CANDLE SharePoint and is accessible to all partners.

A	B	C	D	E	F
Acronym	Organization Name	Name to be used in Communications	Country	Website	LinkedIn
Health-RI	Health-RI		NL	https://www.health-ri.nl/en	https://www.linkedin.com/company/health-ri
Lygature	Stichting Lygature		NL	https://www.lygature.org/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/lygature
ELIXIR	EUROPEAN MOLECULAR BIOLOGY LABORATORY (ELIXIR)	ELIXIR	EU	https://elixir-europe.org/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/elixir-eu
BSC	Barcelona Supercomputing Centre		ES	https://www.bsc.es/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/barcelona-supercomputing-centre
Steinbeis	STEINBEIS INNOVATION GMBH		DE	https://www.steinbeis.de/de/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/steinbeis
Charité	CHARITE - UNIVERSITAETS MEDIZIN BERLIN		DE	https://www.charite.de/	https://de.linkedin.com/school/charite/
EMPIRICA	EMPIRICA		DE	https://empirica.com/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/empirica
HUS-YHTYMA	Finnish Cancer Center FICAN	FICAN	FI	https://fican.fi/en/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/finnish-cancer-center
BBMRI-ERIC	BBMRI-ERIC		EU	https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/bbmri-eric
MOU/MMCI	MASARYKOV ONKOLOGICKY USTAV/Masaryk Memorial Cancer Institute		CZ	https://www.mou.cz/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/mou-brno
EATRIS ERIC	EATRIS ERIC		EU	https://eatris.eu/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eatris-eric
UPOL	UNIVERZITA PALACKEHO V OLOMOUCI		CZ	https://www.upol.cz/en/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/palacky-university-olomouc
ECRIN	ECRIN EUROPEAN CLINICAL RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE NETWORK		EU	https://ecrin.org/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ecrin/
EURO-BIOIMAGING ERIC	EURO-BIOIMAGING ERIC		FI	https://www.eurobioimaging.eu/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/euro-bioimaging-eric
CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE		IT	https://www.cnr.it/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/consiglio-nazionale-delle-ricerche
UU-EIRENE	University Utrecht		NL	https://www.uu.nl/en	https://www.linkedin.com/school/universiteit-utrecht
IKNL	STICHTING INTEGRAAL KANKERCENTRUM NEDERLAND		NL	https://iknl.nl/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/iknl
ECO	European Cancer Organisation		BE	https://www.europeancancer.org/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/european-cancer-organisation

Figure : CANDLE Communication and Dissemination Tracking Tool

The tool contains information on news items and blog posts, events, publications, and synergies, as well as a master list of communication contacts. The news item and blog posts section aims to compile a list of all posts available on the CANDLE official website and social media, as well as on other websites where CANDLE is highlighted. It includes information such as the post type, author, date, a short description of the content, and the link. This section is essential for maintaining an overview of our communication and dissemination activities, as well as CANDLE coverage among partners and beyond.

The event section includes a list of external and internal events, past and planned. It contains details on the event name and type, date, place, audience type, links (if available), the partner responsible, and the extent of our participation. This ensures that we have a comprehensive view of CANDLE's participation in conferences, workshops, and seminars, and that this participation is well documented and, when necessary, followed up on.

The publication tracker helps monitor and disseminate the project's scientific output and research activities by compiling a list of all scientific publications produced by the CANDLE consortium. This page contains information on the title and type of publication, authorship, publication date, DOI, and access information.

The last section of the tracker is reserved for our synergy projects. This page contains information on projects we already have or aim to establish relationships with, at the communication and dissemination levels.

7 Conclusions and next steps

CANDLE helps Member States build a novel institution: the National Cancer Data Nodes. Thus, our communication, dissemination, and exploitation efforts need to align and ensure that target groups know about National Cancer Data Nodes and can find their own way to implement them. It also needs to highlight that the Nodes are not necessarily additional to existing structures, but can be integrated with or merged into them.

While the main outreach target groups are Member State-level institutions likely to set up the National Cancer Data Nodes, other stakeholders are also relevant as potential users or beneficiaries.

This document outlines the strategy to reach these goals and stakeholders. The next important steps for communication, dissemination, and exploitation include:

- Draft D5.2 – Stakeholder engagement strategy and draft personas (M12): based on initial stakeholder mapping in chapter 2 and the first results from stakeholder interactions,
- Drafting of National Cancer Data Nodes Personas: to help T2.1 better define the NCDN users, T4.3 to understand their skill needs better, and also as a communication tool. Reported in D5.2,
- Start policy dialogues (T5.3, start M14): to obtain policy maker feedback on NCDNs and explore pathways to integrate NCDNs in national and European contexts
- Set up the NCDN network (T5.4, start M18): as an engagement structure starting in CANDLE; we intend to make it an exchange space to persist beyond the project end
- Plan the CANDLE Resource Kit (T5.4, start M18): coordinate the ongoing creation of assets for the CANDLE Resource Kit in WPs 2-5